

**МИНИСТЕРСТВО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАУКИ
ДОНЕЦКОЙ НАРОДНОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЕ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЕ ВЫСШЕГО
ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ
«ДОНЕЦКАЯ АКАДЕМИЯ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЫ
ПРИ ГЛАВЕ ДОНЕЦКОЙ НАРОДНОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ»**

**СБОРНИК НАУЧНЫХ РАБОТ
СЕРИИ «ФИНАНСЫ, УЧЁТ, АУДИТ»**

Выпуск 17

**Донецк
2020**

УДК 082.1: 336
ББК Ч25я54 + У26
Г72

Г72 Государственное образовательное учреждение высшего профессионального образования «Донецкая академия управления и государственной службы при Главе Донецкой Народной Республики». Сборник научных работ серии «Финансы, учёт, аудит». Вып. 17 / ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС». – Донецк: ДонАУиГС, 2020. – 266 с.

В сборнике представлены результаты научных исследований. Изложены концептуальные основы формирования финансов хозяйствующих субъектов; приведен методический инструментарий финансирования инновационных и инвестиционных процессов; рассмотрены вопросы развития структурных элементов территориальных и местных финансов, анализа, учёта и аудита в современных условиях; теоретико-методические принципы финансово-банковских механизмов управления экономикой.

Предназначен для научных работников, аспирантов, магистрантов, обучающихся. Представляет интерес для руководителей предприятий, предпринимателей и менеджеров.

УДК 082.1:336
ББК Ч25я54+У26

Сборник научных работ серии «Финансы, учёт, аудит» включён в базу данных Российского индекса научного цитирования (РИНЦ).

Свидетельство о регистрации средства массовой информации Министерства информации Донецкой Народной Республики серии ААА № 000067 от 16.11.2016 г.

В соответствии с решением Высшей аттестационной комиссии Министерства образования и науки Донецкой Народной Республики сборник научных работ серии «Финансы, учёт, аудит» включён в Перечень рецензируемых научных изданий.

Учредитель:

ГОУ ВПО «Донецкая академия управления и государственной службы при Главе Донецкой Народной Республики».

Главный редактор:

Волощенко Л.М. – доктор экономических наук, доцент, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС».

Заместитель главного редактора:

Верига А.В. – доктор экономических наук, доцент, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС».

Редакционная коллегия:

Гончаров В.Н. – доктор экономических наук, профессор, ГОУ ЛНР «Луганский национальный аграрный университет»;

Зенченко Т.В. – доктор экономических наук, профессор кафедры денежного обращения и кредита, Федеральное государственное автономное образовательное учреждение высшего профессионального образования «Северо-Кавказский федеральный университет»;

Кондрашова Т.Н. – кандидат экономических наук, доцент, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС»;

Корнев М.Н. – доктор экономических наук, доцент, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС»;

Нижегородцев Р.М. – доктор экономических наук, Институт проблем управления РАН, Российская Федерация;

Омельченко Е.Ю. – кандидат экономических наук, доцент, Российский экономический университет им. Г.В. Плеханова;

Петренко С.Н. – доктор экономических наук, профессор, ГОУ ВПО «ДонНУЭТ»;

Петрушевская В.В. – доктор экономических наук, доцент, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС»;

Петрушевский Ю.Л. – доктор экономических наук, профессор, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС»;

Пономарёв И.Ф. – доктор экономических наук, профессор, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС»;

Саенко В.Г. – доктор экономических наук, доцент, профессор ГОУ ВПО «ДЮА»;

Саенко В.Б. – кандидат наук государственного управления, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС».

Научный редактор:

Арчигова Я.О. – кандидат экономических наук, доцент, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС».

Технический секретарь:

Волбуева Д.С. – кандидат экономических наук, преподаватель, ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС».

Адрес редакции: ДНР, 83015, г. Донецк, ул. Челюскинцев, д. 163а.

Телефон: (062) 337-66-09.

Издаётся по решению Учёного совета ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС»

© ГОУ ВПО «ДонАУиГС», 2020

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ

Секция 1. ТЕОРИЯ, МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ И КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ФИНАНСОВ ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ

Арчикова Я.О., Алфимова К.А.

Финансовое планирование и прогнозирование как
важнейшие инструменты развития предприятия6

Волобуева Д.С., Якушкина В.А.

Проблемы и перспективы развития малого бизнеса
в Донецкой Народной Республике16

Егоров П.В., Моисеева А.В.

Классификация факторов, влияющих на управление
финансово-экономической гибкостью предприятия28

Филиппова Ю.А., Матвейчук Ю.А.

Особенности управления финансовыми рисками
на предприятии46

Сорокотягина В.Л.

Рекомендации для разработки национального
стандарта по управлению финансовыми рисками
для предприятий малого бизнеса56

Степанчук С.С., Горячих А.Д.

Сущность, значение и классификация финансовых
результатов отечественных предприятий64

Шамкалович Е.Э.

Теоретико-методологические основы финансовой
устойчивости предприятия71

Шилина А.Н., Тарасенко О.В.

Управление прибылью предприятия82

Секция 2. МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЙ ИНСТРУМЕНТАРИЙ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ И ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ

Шарый К.В., Кротинов Д.Ю.

Инновационная деятельность предприятия: проблемы
и пути решения.....94

Шумаева Е.А., Подбуцкий А.А.

Повышение эффективности деятельности промышленного
сектора путём его инновационного развития102

Секция 3. РАЗВИТИЕ СТРУКТУРНЫХ ЭЛЕМЕНТОВ ТЕРРИТОРИАЛЬНЫХ И МЕСТНЫХ ФИНАНСОВ

Курган Е.Г., Чванов С.А.

Развитие института профессионального образования
в Донецкой Народной Республике.....114

Романинец Р.Н., Мирской С.И.

Теневая экономика как одна из ключевых угроз
экономической безопасности125

Сподарёва Е.Г., Пак Л.В.

Механизм управления финансовыми ресурсами
внебюджетных137

Хистева Е.В.

К вопросу создания государственного корпоративного
сектора в Донецкой Народной Республике155

Чегодаев Б.В., Чегодаева Ю.С.

Генезис теории управления качеством:
историческая справка170

Petrushevskaya V., Brovar N.

Comparative analysis of financial systems:
Russia and DPR186

Секция 4. ВОПРОСЫ АНАЛИЗА, УЧЁТА И АУДИТА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ

Агафоненко О.Ю.

Анализ показателей и критерия эффективности
региональной конкурентоспособности..... 194

Бондаренко О.В.

Информационно-аналитическое обеспечение субъектов
малого предпринимательства 204

Верига А.В.

Развитие контроля расчётов с подотчётными лицами
в Донецкой Народной Республике 214

Мехедова Т.Н., Макаркина С.В.

Актуальные аспекты внутреннего аудита как
инструмента внутреннего контроля расчётов
по оплате труда в бюджетных учреждениях..... 231

Секция 5. РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕОРЕТИКО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИХ ПРИНЦИПОВ ФИНАНСОВО-БАНКОВСКИХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИКОЙ

Ангелина И.А., Салита С.В.

Финансы в условиях цифровой экономики:
тенденции развития..... 240

Гордеева Н.В., Попова А.А.

Управление банковскими рисками
в современных условиях 253

СССР 10 июля 1940 года [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://ru.wikisource.org> (дата обращения: 02.07.2019).

8. Сталин о проблемах военной промышленности СССР [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://colonelcassad.livejournal.com/4374406.html>

9. ГОСТ Р ИСО 9001-2015 Системы менеджмента качества. Требования. – М.: Стандартинформ, 2015. – 24 с.

10. ГОСТ Р 56577-2015 Системы менеджмента качества органов власти. Требования. – М.: Стандартинформ, 2015. – 32 с.

11. Указ Главы Донецкой Народной Республики № 399 от 22.11.2016 г. – Донецк, 2016 [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://dnr-online.ru/download/ukaz-glavy-donetskoj-narodnoj-respubliki-399-ot-22-11-2016-goda-o-primenenii-standartov-na-territorii-donetskoj-narodnoj-respubliki/>.

УДК 336.1

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL SYSTEMS: RUSSIA AND DPR

Petrushevskaya V.,
A.P.E.S., Professor,

Professor of the Department of «Finance»

SEI HPE «Donetsk Academy of Management and Public Administration
under the Head of Donetsk People’s Republic», city of Donetsk;

Brovar N.,

first-year post-graduate of the Department of Finance and
Banking of Donetsk National University

The article deals with the main aspects of the functioning of the financial system in the Russian economy and the economy in the Donetsk people's Republic.

Keywords: *financial system, state and municipal finances, finances of economic entities.*

Problem statement. For the growth and stability of the economy of any country, for a successful the functioning and development of the entire market economy, it is necessary to have a reliable financial system. It serves as the basis for the entire existing economy and undoubtedly plays a very important role.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The study of the financial system paid attention to the following scientists: Van Horn J.K [1], McConnell K.R [2], J. Wachowich. M [3], Lomakin V. K. [4] and others. However, today a number of issues on the functioning of the financial system remain unresolved.

Topicality. Consideration of the directions of development of the financial system of states, which is one of the most important factors of economic growth. The problem of functioning of the financial system in the modern world is very relevant, because the development of the state depends on its solution.

Purpose of article. The study of the foundations of the functioning of the financial system of the state, as well as the actions necessary for its development.

Presentation of the main research material. The financial system is a set of relatively separate interrelated financial relations that reflect specific forms and methods of GDP distribution.

Considering the financial system of a country, there are two levels: micro-and macro-level.

The micro level of the financial system involves the study of the activities of financial institutions (organizations), the laws of financial markets and ways to manage both.

The macro level includes the study of large-scale financial processes such as, for example, the objectives and methods of monetary and fiscal policy.

The main objective of the financial system is to create such financial conditions under which the reproduction of the national product will be carried out with full employment and low inflation [5].

Let's analyze the scope and parts of Russia. In the financial system of the Russian Federation there are three major areas: state and municipal finances; finances of economic entities; household finances.

Let's consider in more detail the spheres and links of Russia.

State and municipal finances are monetary relations arising in the distribution process in connection with the formation and use of funds intended to support the activities of state authorities and local government.

The sphere of state and municipal Finance includes five links: the budget Fund; the Federal budget; budgets of the subjects of the Russian Federation; budgets of municipalities.

Pic. 1. Spheres and links of the financial system of the Russian Federation

The budget fund is a centralized monetary Fund designed to Finance a wide range of public needs – sectors of economy, social needs, management, defense, etc.

The Federal budget on the material maintenance is the main Fund of money of the state. Its leading role is largely due to the fact that the Federal budget produces the main expenditures of the state: for military purposes; management; law enforcement; intervention in the economy; social spending; subsidies, etc. The budgets of other levels of the budget system of the Russian Federation are also leveled at the expense of the Federal budget.

Budgets of subjects of the Russian Federation. Each subject of the Russian Federation has its own regional budget. Subject of reference and powers of subjects of the Federation in the budgetary area are regulated by contracts (agreements) about differentiation of subjects of reference

and powers between public authorities of the Russian Federation and public authorities of the subject of the Federation.

The local budget is a form of formation and expenditure of money in calculation for financial year intended for maintenance of the tasks and functions carried to subjects of conducting local government, by execution of expenditure obligations of the corresponding municipal formation.

The finances of business entities are monetary relations arising in the process of formation, distribution and use of cash funds and accumulations as a result of production and sale of goods, work and various services. The finances of economic entities are the basis of the financial system, since it is in this area that the predominant share of the country's financial resources is formed.

In the sphere of finance of economic entities there are three levels: finance of commercial organizations, finance of non-profit organizations and finance of individual entrepreneurs.

Commercial finance organizations in the finance of economic entities is key, as commercial organizations create wealth, produce goods, provide services, formed a profit – the main source of socio-economic development of society.

Finances of non-profit organizations are characterized by a wide variety of sources of funding, the specifics of income generation, the order of their use. Non-profit economic goals require such organizations not only to develop their own profitable activities, but also to attract external sources of funding from the state, the population and the private sector.

Finance of individual entrepreneurs is a special link of the financial system associated with the formation and use of financial resources of citizens in order to ensure their business activities [6].

Household finance is a monetary relationship about the distribution of the value of a public product and the formation of income and expenditure of the population. The sphere of household finance is not divided into independent units.

Household finances are closely linked to the finances of other sectors and parts of the country's financial system through tax payments, transactions with government and corporate securities, public participation in credit transactions, etc.

We will also analyze the financial system of the DPR.

Pic. 2. Spheres and links of the DPR financial system

The first field of the financial system DNR is Finance of economic entities is relatively independent sphere of the system of Finance of the state, covering a wide range of monetary relations connected with formation and use of capital, income, funds in the process of circulation of funds and expressed in the form of various cash flows.

The second sphere of the financial system of the DPR is the state and municipal finances - a set of economic relations arising in real money turnover on the formation, distribution and use of centralized funds of financial resources. Summing up the analysis of the financial system of States, we can say that each state has its own spheres and links and their characteristics . Russia has a more developed financial system [7].

Conclusions on this study and directions for further development on this problem. On the basis of studies of various economic processes in Russia, 3 main problems can be identified, the solution of which contributes to the revival of the financial sphere of society. These include:

- the problem of «raw material nature» of the Russian economy;
- the problem of the «shadow economy»;
- the problem of household Finance development.

Consider the essence of each problem and analyze the ways and methods by which they can be solved. The problem of raw material nature of the Russian economy. The strong influence of oil and gas due to the raw material nature of the Russian economy creates risks for the development of the Russian financial system.

Such dependence leads to the following consequences: when the price of oil decreases, revenues of the state budget decrease, purchasing power of the national currency unit decreases, there is a need for the state to borrow funds from external and domestic sources, inflation risks arise.

There are some ways to solve this problem:

Diversification of the sphere of production for more dynamic development of economic entities, acceleration of economic growth, increase of the share of non-commodity revenues of the budget of the Russian Federation;

Development of investment and financial markets with a view to improving the redistribution of financial resources and attracting investments in the real sector of the economy, which will allow domestic enterprises to develop more effectively.

The problem of the shadow economy. The shadow economy negatively affects the development of small and medium-sized businesses in the country, leads to distortion of business activity indicators, reduction of the revenue part of the country's budget. Practice has shown that with the increase in crisis phenomena, the scale of shadow economic relations is increasing, and the labour force is moving into the informal sector. This negatively affects the development of productive forces and industrial relations and the economic growth of the state as a whole.

We can suggest the following solutions to this problem:

Improvement of the legislative framework, as the presence of a shadow economy is primarily related to the possibility of "falling into the shadow" due to an imperfect legislative framework;

Stabilization of the economic and political situation, which will contribute to the revival of business activity, prevention of recession in the economy, increase of employment of the population and its confidence in the state.

Problem of household finance development. Household finance plays an important role both in the development of the country's solvent demand and in the development of centralized finance through tax payments. The higher the income of the population, the higher its demand for various types of material and intangible benefits and the greater the opportunities for economic and social development.

In order to increase the efficiency of households in solving social problems in society, the State, in our view, needs:

To increase the income of the population, first of all, by establishing fair wages.

Thus, despite the positive changes in the financial system of the Russian Federation, there are a number of problems that need to be solved in order to improve the economic relations between the links of the financial system and to ensure further economic growth.

Problems and solutions of the financial system in the DPR.

At the moment we can identify a number of problems of the financial system of the DPR:

the problem of restoring the credit functions of the banking system;
the problem of creating an independent financial and budgetary system;

the problem of household Finance development.

The problem of restoring the broken credit functions of the banking system depends on three components:

possibility of obtaining external credit resources;
the possibility of internal accumulation for the development of credit.

Obtaining DPR external loans is simplified due to the zero public debt of the DPR, but complicated by the status of an unrecognized state. This section rests, first of all, not in economic, but in political restrictions, and requires a separate negotiating platform, primarily with the Russian Federation, headed by a negotiator (head of delegation) of high level and qualification.

The solution may be to create an export-import Bank registered in foreign jurisdictions, attracting credit resources for export supplies. The success of this project directly rests on the creation of national fuel and metallurgical export concerns that have a monopoly on the export of energy and metals abroad.

To solve the problem in the development of household finances, it is necessary to ensure the growth of incomes of the population in the first place, through the establishment of fair wages [8].

Based on this, we can conclude that at this stage development of the financial system of Russia and the DPR continues to be formed, defining for itself new ways of development and tasks for improving the efficiency of financial relations.

Thus, the state of the financial system depends not only on the decisions taken by the authorities, which are focused on integration into the financial and political sphere, but also from the population itself, the

local governments, entrepreneurs in the framework of local payment systems, as well as forms of collective financing.

Literature

1. Van Horn, George.K. Fundamentals of financial management / Van Horn John.K. – Moscow: «Finance and credit», 2003. – 788 p.
2. McConnell K.R. Economics / McConnell K.R., brew S. L. – M.: «INFRA-M», 1999. – 984 p.
3. Van Horn, George.K. Fundamentals of financial management / van horn J.K., J. Wachowich.M. «I.D. Williams», 2008 – 1232 p.
4. Lomakin V.K. World economy / V.K. Lomakin. – M.: «UNITY-DANA», 2007. – 545 p.
5. Berlin S.I. Theory of Finance / S.I. Berlin. – M: «Prior», 2017. – 235 p.
6. Dadashev A.Z. Financial system Russia / A.Z. Dadashev, D.G. Chernik. – M: «INFRA-M», 1997. – 350 p.
7. Donetsk revolution. Articles and papers (2014-2016) / B.A. Borisov [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: http://www.rumvi.com/products/ebook/донецкая-революция-статьи-и-документы-2014-2016-гг-/cd0f58eb-b7fb-4c66-bc83a6879d0a63ef/preview/preview.html#ТОС_EIKAC
8. Kovaleva V.V. Finance money circulation loans / V.V. Kovaleva. – M: «Yurait», 2006. – 543 p.

Научное издание

**ГОУ ВПО «Донецкая академия управления и государственной службы
при Главе Донецкой Народной Республики»**

СБОРНИК НАУЧНЫХ РАБОТ

СЕРИИ «ФИНАНСЫ, УЧЁТ, АУДИТ»

Выпуск 17

Материалы представлены на языке оригинала.

Опубликованные материалы отражают точку зрения авторов,
которая может не совпадать с мнением редколлегии сборника.

При цитировании или частичном использовании текста публикаций
ссылка на сборник обязательна.

Ответственная за выпуск	Волощенко Л.М.
Литературный редактор	Кравченко А.В.
Технический редактор	Волобуева Д.С.
Компьютерная вёрстка	Зензеров В.И.

Подписано в печать 26.03.2020 г.

Формат 60x841/16 Бумага офсетная 15,4 усл.-печ. л. Тираж 100 экз.

ГОУ ВПО «Донецкая академия управления и государственной
службы при Главе Донецкой Народной Республики»

Адрес редакции: ДНР, 83015, г. Донецк, ул. Челюскинцев,
163а ГОУ ВПО «ДонаУиГС»